

Halogenation. Part XIV. Iodination of Aromatic Hydrocarbons and Bromotoluenes.

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The iodination of aromatic hydrocarbons in presence of (i) a mixture of fuming nitric acid and fuming nitrosulphonic acid or (ii) sodium nitrite and fuming sulphuric acid has been described in previous communications (Varma, Kulkarni and Panickar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **3**, 291, 342). In the present paper the iodination of aromatic hydrocarbons in presence of a mixture of fuming nitric acid and fuming sulphuric acid are described. In this reaction nitro compounds are also formed, but by using a small excess of fuming sulphuric acid, their formation is avoided.

The iodination of the three bromotoluenes in presence of nitrosulphonic acid (*vide* Varma and Venkatraman, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 244) is also described. The mono-iodo compounds obtained are identical with the compounds obtained by previous workers by other methods (*cf.* Hurtz, *Ber.*, 1896, **29**, 1405; Cohen and Miller, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, **85**, 1627; Wroblewski, *Annalen*, 1873, **168**, 164, 169).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Iodobenzene.—Benzene (15 c. c.), iodine (10 g.) and glacial acetic (20 c. c.) were heated under a reflux condenser on a water-bath and a mixture of fuming nitric acid (6 g.) and fuming sulphuric acid (8 g.) was added to the contents of the flask in portions of 10 drops at a time and the heating continued for 2½ hours. The product of the reaction was then washed free from acid, dried over calcium chloride and distilled; 12 g. of iodobenzene, b. p. 186-189°, were obtained.

Toluene (15 c. c.), iodine (10 g.), fuming HNO₃ (5.4 g.), fuming H₂SO₄ (7.6 g.); yield 12.7 g. of *o*-iodotoluene.

p-Xylene (15 c. c.), iodine (10 g.), fuming HNO_3 (6.0 g.), fuming H_2SO_4 (7 g.); yield 8.5 g. of 2-iodo-*p*-xylene.

o-Xylene (15 c. c.), iodine (10 g.), fuming HNO_3 (4.8 g.), fuming H_2SO_4 (5.2 g.); yield 8.2 g. of 4-iodo-*o*-xylene.

m-Xylene (15 c. c.), iodine (10 g.), fuming HNO_3 (5.5 g.), fuming H_2SO_4 (6.7 g.); yield 11.8 g of 4-iodo-*m*-xylene.

Ethylbenzene (15 c. c.), iodine (10 g.), fuming HNO_3 (6.0 g.) fuming H_2SO_4 (7.6 g.); yield 2.3 g. of 4-iodoethylbenzene.

Pseudocumene (15 c. c.), iodine (10 g.), fuming HNO_3 (6.4 g.), fuming H_2SO_4 (7.6 g.); yield 2.0 c. c. of 5-iodopseudocumene.

2-Bromo-4-iodotoluene.—To a mixture of *o*-bromotoluene (5 c. c.), iodine (5 g.) and chloroform (10 c. c.) heated in a flask with a reflux condenser on a sand-bath, nitrosulphonic acid mixture (2.8 c.c.) was added drop by drop from the top of the condenser. The flask was heated for 6 hours at about 170-180°, allowed to cool, washed free of iodine by 2 % solution of sodium hydroxide, dried over fused calcium chloride and distilled. The product distilling between 265-267° was found to be pure 2-bromo-4-iodotoluene, yield 6.5 g.

3-Bromo-4-iodotoluene.—*m*-Bromotoluene (5 c. c.), iodine (5 g.), glacial acetic acid (15 c. c.) and chloroform (10 c. c.) were heated on a sand-bath in a flask for 10 minutes. When the contents began to boil, nitrosulphonic acid mixture (3 c. c.) was added in a portion of 0.5 c. c. every 10 minutes. The flask was heated on the whole for 4 hours at about 180-190°. The product was purified as in the preceding case and the fraction distilling between 265-267° was identified to be 3-bromo-4-iodotoluene, yield 7.4 g.

4-Bromo-2-iodotoluene.—*p*-Bromotoluene on similar treatment gave 4-bromo-2-iodotoluene (3.4 g.) distilling at 262-267°.